

CAUSES, CONSEQUENCES AND COUNSELLING STRATEGIES FOR CURBING SOCIAL MEDIA ADDICTION AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN OYI LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA

**Alphonsus Ekejiuba Oguzie, Ph.D, Eberechukwu Francisca Chigbu, Ph.D,
Nwobi Ngozika Lovina, Ph.D and Obianuju Blessing Mokuwelu, Ph.D**

*Department of Guidance and Counselling, Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka,
Anambra State.*

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ABSTRACT: *This study investigated the causes, consequences and counselling strategies for curbing social media addiction among secondary school students in Oyi Local Government Area. Three research questions guided the study. The study adopted the descriptive survey design, and the population comprised of forty-seven (47) counsellors in all the public secondary schools in Oyi LGA. The entire population was used in the study without sampling because it was manageable by the researcher. The instrument used in collecting data was a structured questionnaire titled Causes, Consequences and Counselling Strategies for Curbing Social Media Addiction Questionnaire (CCSSMAQ). The instrument was validated by experts in Department of Guidance and Counselling and Measurements and Evaluation. Arithmetic mean was used for analysis of data. The findings from the study showed that the causes of social media addiction among secondary school students in Oyi LGA are low self-esteem, fear of missing out, peer influence, poor parental supervision, loneliness, instant gratification from social media and impulsivity. However, the findings showed that gender is not the causes of social media addiction among secondary school students in the area. The findings of the study equally showed that the consequences of social media addiction among students in Oyi LGA are poor academic achievement, social isolation, depression, drug abuse, health problems such as eye strain, headache and fatigue, Interpersonal relationship problems, cyber fraud and sleeping disturbance, while low self-esteem, suicidal ideation and expose to cyberbullying are not part of the consequences of social media addiction among students in Oyi local government area. Finally, the results of the study revealed that the counselling strategies for curbing social media addiction among secondary school students in Oyi LGA are assertiveness training technique, self-management technique, social skill training, use of stimulus satiation on addicted students, cognitive behaviour therapy, bibliotherapeutic materials, cognitive restructuring and modelling techniques, while use of positive reinforcement and systematic desensitization techniques are not part of the techniques used for curbing social media addiction in the area. It was recommended among others, that School Counsellors should ensure kin and objective observation on students' behaviours and guard against such behaviour that could engender social media addiction among secondary school students.*

**Alphonsus Ekejiuba Oguzie, Ph.D, Eberechukwu Francisca Chigbu, Ph.D, Nwobi
Ngozika Lovina, Ph.D and Obianuju Blessing Mokuwelu, Ph.D**

Introduction

Social media appears to be the fastest growing and dominant trend in the use of technology among modern day students. This is because social media is used to perform various functions across all levels of education, especially in secondary schools. As students make use of the social media in their daily academic activities, they tend to become engulfed by the use of social media platforms. Subsequently, such students may begin to find very difficult to survive without the use of social media. cc

Social media refers to as a variety of technologies that facilitate the sharing of ideas and information among their users. It is a collective term for websites and applications that focus on communication, community-based input, interaction, content-sharing and collaboration (Lutkevich & Wigmore, 2023). According to Zahrai, Veer, Ballantine, Vries and Prayag (2022), social media is an online platform that allows people to communicate with one another electronically. Dollarhide and Drury (2023) defined social media as a digital technology that facilitates the sharing of ideas, thoughts and information through virtual networks and communities. In the context of this study, social media are interactive technologies that facilitate the creation, sharing and aggregation of content , ideas, interests, and other forms of expression through virtual communities and networks.

Currently, social media is one of the fastest growing media platforms, with more than 4.7 billion users globally (Dollarhide & Drury, 2023). Perhaps, this is because it provides users immediate and easy access to information at all times. Social media makes it easier for people to communicate with one another online. Hence, social media has been embraced by individuals in

all areas of human endeavour as a veritable instrument for communication worldwide. As a result of this, many individuals including students make use of the social media in their day to day activities. Students may use social media for various reasons. For example, some students use it to communicate ideas, feelings, personal information, and to send pictures, while others use social media for the purpose of communicating with families and friends, keeping up with happenings and events of the daily life, and also for academic purposes. Social media can offer academic assistance and support to students as it provides quick access to virtual space which students can explore with friends having similar academic needs (Ikwuka, Egwu, Onimisi & Okeke, 2018).

In reality, students may access social media services through web-based apps on desktops or download services that offer social media functionality to their mobile devices. Examples of social media applications or platforms include Facebook, Twitter, Whatsapp, Instagram, YouTube, TikTok, Snapchat, LinkedIn and Quora. These platforms allow users to share contents, communicate online and create communities (Fadeyi & Dare, 2023). As a consequence, social media usage has become endemic and indispensably significant in students' lives because it creates easy interactive platforms in which individuals, groups, and organizations can share, discuss and participate in various activities online. With the various functions that social media offers, such as allowing users to present themselves to others, building new relationships and maintaining existing ones, some students tend to be tempted to spend excessive amount of time to social

media platforms, and eventually become addicted to it.

Social media addiction is the excessive use of networking platforms, disrupting daily activities and personal well-being (Ivanova, 2025). Bhatt (2023) defined social media addiction as a behavioural addiction characterized by being overly concerned about social media, driven by an uncontrollable urge to log on to or use social media, and devoting so much time and effort to social media that it impairs other important life areas. It is a compulsive and excessive use of social media to the extent that such users become so accustomed to scrolling through posts, images, and videos that it interferes with other areas of their lives (Legg, 2022). By implication, social media addiction may ignite similar reaction in the brain as gambling and recreational drugs do.

Character wise, Leong, Lee and Hew (2019) observed that individuals who are addicted to social media are always thinking about online activities, wishing to use the internet for an increasing amount of time to obtain satisfaction, unable to control, reduce, or discontinue using social media, feeling restless, depressed, or irritable when reducing social media activities, as well as coping with problems. Jelinek (2022) stated that when a person engages in a pleasurable activity such as the use of social media, the brain releases a hormone called dopamine, which is responsible for feelings of pleasure. Therefore, when an individual receives certain social media notifications, such as a like, share, retweet or comment, the brain may increase their dopamine level. This could cause the individual

to experience a pleasurable feeling, positively reinforcing additional social media use. For the purpose of this study, social media addiction is simply defined as an impulsive behaviour problem where students feel unable to do without social media.

Overtime, social media addiction is a growing problem, particularly among young people of which secondary school students are included. Zahrai, Veer, Ballantine, Vries and Prayag (2022) adduced that social media use has altered the daily routines of almost half the world's population, with an average user spending more than four hours, twenty five minutes on social media daily. Similarly, Sahranc and Ducurhan (2021) observed that students spent an average of 6 hours a day on social media. In fact, psychologists estimated that up to 10% of students are addicted to social media (Legg, 2021). A study by (Lee, 2021) showed that 40 percent of online users aged 18 to 22 years reported feeling addicted to social media.

Evidence in literature have shown that there is an undeniable link between social media addiction and various academic, social and personal problems. For example, Zahrai, Veer, Ballantine, Vries and Prayag (2022) observed that addiction to social media undermines users' psychological well-being resulting in negative outcomes such as ruined relationships, feelings of loneliness and depression, low self-esteem, and other behavioural problems. Yazici and Kumcagiz (2021) in their study reported that students who are addicted to social media experience anxiety because of missing something online, maintaining relationships, instant social comparisons, and conflicts due to openness to

everyone. Also, a study by Durak (2018) showed that social media addiction is related to academic procrastination, self-regulation, and social anxiety. Another study by Miller (2022) revealed that students who addicted to social media may be at heightened risk for mental health problems.

Moreso, social media addiction may lead to interpersonal problems, such as ignoring real life relationships, work or school responsibilities and physical health. Due to the amount of time students spend on social media, there may be a negative effect on their academic activities and personal relationships. Social media addicted students may feel an overwhelming concern about social media and devote a large amount of time to it, thereby overlooking their academic tasks. A study by Demir and Kumcagiz (2019) showed that students who are addicted to social media usually perform poor in their academics. Ndubuaku, Inim, Ndudi, Udo and Abner (2020) stated that social media addiction is linked to poor academic performance, health challenges, interpersonal relationship problems and responsibilities related issues. In addition, Andreassen and Pallesen (2014) suggested that individuals addicted to social media may have low ability to plan and organize their personal lives.

Generally, social media addition has become a serious social, academic and public health problem especially among students in Anambra state, especially those in Oyi local government area. Moreso, the researcher's personal observation during her Practicum exercise shows that some secondary school students in Oyi are always

glued to their phones using social media even during lesson periods. Based on this reason, the present study was initiated to find out the causes, consequences and counselling strategies for curbing social addiction among secondary school students in Oyi local government area.

Statement of the Problem

Social media addiction has assumed a serious global challenge that could have pervasive negative consequences on the psychological, academic and social functioning of youths and students in the present society. Generally, schools are considered as hubs for transformational learning and life skills. In this regard, students are expected to adopt only positive behaviours that would help them function properly in their social and academic environment. In the time past, students in Oyi local government area were known for their spirit of dexterity, prudence and diligence. Those days, students were always seen busy in their classrooms, laboratories and libraries studying with maximum concentration.

However, the trend seems to have changed towards the opposite direction in recent times, as the increasing rate of social media addiction among students in our schools has posed serious worries to parents, teachers, researchers and the society in general. Ideally, as people who are in their middle level of education, secondary school students are supposed to be devoted to their studies and try to avoid any event or activity that is capable of causing distraction to their academic endeavour. There is no doubt, that social media addiction has become a serious problem among students in this present-day

society. Oftentimes students in Oyi local government area are found are busy pressing phone while lessons are going on in their classrooms. Others tend to leave their classrooms and hang around the school premises in order not to miss out in live social media events, at the detriment of their academics.

Moreso, because of social media, some secondary school students in Oyi local government area tend to waste a whole lot of time, lose concentration in their studies and eventually begin to perform poor in their social and academic lives. Different measures have been put in place by parents, teachers and school principals to curb the problem of social media addiction among students. Such measures which are mostly punitive include seizing of android and smart phones, flogging, cutting grasses, kneeling down under the hot sun, suspension and even total rustication of students caught using the social media during lesson hours. Unfortunately, these efforts of parents, teachers and principals seem to have met with little success when compared with the number of students addicted to social media in Oyi local government area.

Therefore, the problem of this study is that, despite the efforts in place to curb social media addiction in Anambra State, especially in Oyi local government area the menace is still increasing exponentially. Thus, a very important question that is waiting for an empirically generated answer here is; what are the causes, consequences and counselling intervention strategies that could be effectively used to solve the problem of social media addiction? The current researchers believed that a survey study

of this nature seeking to explore the causes, consequences and counselling strategies may provide an answer to the above question and help in bringing a lasting solution to the problem of social media addiction among students in Oyi local government area.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What are the causes of social media addiction among secondary school students in Oyi local government area?
2. What are the consequences of social media addiction among secondary school students in Oyi local government area?
3. What are the counselling strategies for curbing social media addiction among secondary school students in Oyi local government area?

Method

This study was carried out in Oyi Local Governments Area of Anambra State. This study adopted the descriptive survey design. Descriptive survey research design is one in which a group of people is studied by collecting and analyzing data from only a few group of the people considered to the representative sample of the entire group. Descriptive survey study involves collection of data and describing in a systematic manner the characteristics, features or facts about a given population. The population of the study consisted of 47 guidance counsellors in all the public secondary schools in Oyi Local Government Area (Post Primary School Service Commission (PPSSC), 2025). The researchers used the entire population of the study as sample because it was manageable and there was no need for further sampling. Adeyemo (2013)

recommended that if the population of a study is small, it should be studied entirely.

The instrument used in collecting data for the study was structured questionnaire designed by the researcher. The instrument is titled "Causes, Consequences and Counselling Strategies for Curbing Social Media Addiction Questionnaire (CCCSSMAQ)". The instrument consists of three clusters; i, ii and iii. The first cluster sought the opinion of the respondents regarding the causes of social media addiction required to answer research question one, cluster two sought the opinion of the respondents regarding the consequences of social media addiction required to answer research question two, while the third cluster sought the opinion of the respondents regarding the counselling strategies for curbing social media addiction among secondary school students required to answer research question three. The instrument has a total of 29 items based on the four- point scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). To ascertain the validity of the instrument, two copies of the questionnaire including the title, purpose of the study and

Results

Table 1: Mean rating of respondents on the causes of social media addiction among secondary school students in Oyi LGA

S/N	Causes of Social media addiction	Mean	Remark
1.	Low self-esteem	2.74	Agree
2.	Fear of missing out	2.61	Agree
3.	Peer influence	3.00	Agree
4.	Poor parental supervision	2.72	Agree
5.	Loneliness	2.58	Agree
6.	Instant gratification from social media	2.91	Agree

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research questions were given to three experts. The experts were specifically requested to access the clarity of language, logical sequence of the items, adequacy and appropriateness of the items to generate data required to answer the research questions. The corrections and suggestions of the experts were used to in modifying the final copy of the instrument. The reliability of the instrument was ascertained through a trail test was carried out. Copies of the instrument were administered to 20 counsellors in public universities in a nearby state, which is outside the study area. The instrument was re-administered to the counsellors after two weeks. Cronbach Alpha coefficients of 0.72, 0.81 and 0.76 were obtained for clusters 1, 2 and 3, respectively. Moreso, the overall reliability estimate obtained for the instrument was 0.74. The instrument was therefore considered reliable enough to be used for the study. Data for the study was collected through direct delivery method (DDM) with the help of three research assistants. Data collected for the study was analyzed using arithmetic mean with a benchmark mean of 2.50.

7.	Gender	2.02	Disagree
8.	Impulsivity	2.61	Agree

From table 1 above, it is observed that items 1, 2, 3,4,5,6 and 8 obtained mean rating above the criterion mean of 2.50, while item 7 obtained mean rating less than the criterion mean. This indicates that the respondents agreed that the

factors in items 1,2,3,4,5,6 and 8 are the causes of social media addiction among secondary school students, while they disagreed that the factors in item 7 are causes of social media addiction among students in Oyi LGA.

Table 2: Mean rating of respondents on the consequences of social media among secondary school students in Oyi LGA

S/N	Consequences of Social media addiction	Mean	Remark
9.	Poor academic achievement	2.90	Agree
10.	Social isolation	3.08	Agree
11.	Depression	3.01	Agree
12.	Drug abuse	2.79	Agree
13.	Health problems such as eye strain, headache and fatigue	2.58	Agree
14.	Low self-esteem	2.06	Disagree
15.	Suicidal ideation	1.64	Disagree
16.	Interpersonal relationship problems	2.78	Agree
17.	Expose to cyberbullying	1.74	Disagree
18.	Cyber fraud	2.82	Agree
19.	Sleep disturbances	2.76	Agree

Data in table 2 showed that all the items 9,10,11,12,13,16,18 and 19 obtained mean rating above the criterion mean of 2.50, while items 14, 15 and 17 obtained mean rating below the criterion mean. This implies that the respondents agreed that the problems presented

in items 9,10,11,12,13,16,18 and 19 are the consequences of social media addiction among secondary school students, while they disagreed that the problems in items 14,15 and 17 are consequences of social media addiction among secondary school students in Oyi LGA.

Table 3: Mean rating of respondents on the counselling strategies for curbing social media addiction among secondary school students in Oyi LGA

S/N	counselling strategies for social media addiction	Mean	Remark
20.	Assertiveness training technique	2.72	Agree
21.	Self-management technique	2.69	Agree
22.	Use of positive reinforcement	2.01	Disagree

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23.	Social skill training	3.00	Agree
24.	Use of stimulus satiation on addicted students	2.81	Agree
25.	Cognitive behaviour therapy	2.75	Agree
26.	Bibliotherapeutic materials	2.82	Agree
27.	Systematic desensitization	1.46	Disagree
28.	Cognitive restructuring technique	2.64	Agree
29.	Modelling technique	3.00	Agree

Data presented in table 3 revealed that items (20, 21, 23, 24, 25, 26, 28 and 29) obtained mean rating above the criterion mean of 2.50, while items 22 and 27 are less than the criterion mean. This implies that the strategies presented in items 20, 21, 23, 24, 25, 26, 28 and 29 are counselling strategies for curbing social media addiction among secondary school students in Oyi LGA, while the strategies presented in items 22 and 29 are not counselling strategies used by counsellors in curbing social media addiction among students in Oyi local government area.

Discussion of Findings

Considering the results of the analysis of data made in the study starting with the research questions:

The first research question sought to find out the causes of social media addiction among secondary school students in Oyi Local Government Area as perceived school counsellors in the area. The findings showed that the respondents agreed that items (1,2,3,4,5,6 and 8) can cause to social media addiction among the students. Hence, the respondents indicated that low self-esteem, fear of missing out, peer influence, poor parental supervision, loneliness, instant gratification from social media and impulsivity are the key factors that cause shyness among their students. The finding of this study agrees with the report of previous

researchers (Baker & Oswald, 2014; Lee-Won, Herzog & Gwan, 2015; Sahranc & Ducurhan, 2021) that found out that social media addiction can emanate from low self-esteem, fear of missing out, peer influence, poor parental supervision, loneliness, instant gratification from social media and impulsivity. This result is also in consonance with the report by Unachukwu and Iweanya (2021) who in their study observed that students' gender was not among the causes of their social media addiction. The second research questions examined consequences of social media addiction among secondary school students in Oyi local government area. The findings revealed that all the items (9,10,11,12,13,16,18 and 19) in the questionnaires are elicited by social media addiction among secondary school students. Most importantly, the respondents strongly agreed that poor academic achievement, social isolation, depression, drug abuse, health problems such as eye strain, headache and fatigue, Interpersonal relationship problems, cyber fraud and sleeping disturbance are the major consequences of social media addiction among students. This finding is in line with previous report by (Nadkarni & Hofmann, 2014; Wilson, Gosling & Graham, 2015; Habermann, 2021;) who pointed out the consequences of social media addiction are poor academic

achievement, social isolation, depression, drug abuse, health problems such as eye strain, headache and fatigue, Interpersonal relationship problems, cyber fraud and sleeping disturbance. Ahmed and Zakaria (2019) in their study observed that social media addiction causes people to lose track of time while completing assignments, feel lazy to learn, experience anxiety when a new notification comes in, and lack of sleep, resulting in a lack of motivation to wake up early to go to school due to a late wake up.

However, it is important to note that the findings of this study indicated that low self-esteem, suicidal ideation and expose to cyberbullying are not part of the consequences of social media addiction among students. This finding disagrees with the finding by (Balakrishnan & Griffiths, 2017; Nnamani, 2023) that concluded that low self-esteem, suicidal ideation and expose to cyberbullying do not actually emanate from social media addiction.

Finally, the last research question examined the counselling strategies for curbing social media addiction among students in Oyi Local Government Area. The findings shows that the respondents agreed to items (20, 21, 23, 24, 25, 26, 28 and 29) are counselling strategies for curbing social media addiction among secondary school students in Oyi LGA, while the strategies presented in items 22 and 27 are not counselling strategies used by counsellors in curbing social media addiction among students in the area. This indicates that assertiveness training technique, self-management technique, social skill training, use of stimulus satiation on addicted students, cognitive behaviour therapy, bibliotherapeutic

materials, cognitive restructuring and modelling techniques are the counselling strategies for curbing social media addiction among secondary school students in Oyi local government area, while positive reinforcement and systematic desensitization techniques are not part of the techniques used for curbing social media addiction in the area. This result supports the findings by (Tromholt, 2016; Vally & D'Souza, 2019; Hall, Xing, Ross & Johnson 2021; Faulhaber, Lee & Gentile, 2023) who in their various research found that assertiveness training technique, self-management technique, social skill training, use of stimulus satiation on addicted students, cognitive behaviour therapy, bibliotherapeutic materials, cognitive restructuring and modelling techniques are the counselling strategies that can be used to curb among students. Moreso, (Habermann, 2021; Khan & Moin, 2021) observed that providing self-management which is a part of self-management technique is often used to increase the likelihood for a social media addicted student to overcome the compulsive urge for social media use. However, this study found that positive reinforcement and systematic desensitization techniques are not among the techniques used for curbing social media addiction. This finding supports the findings by previous researchers (Gentile, Reimer, Nathanson, Walsh & Eisenmann, 2014; Loftin, Gibb & Skiba, 2022) who concluded that counsellors need to explore more effective counselling strategies for curbing social media addiction among students than positive reinforcement and systematic desensitization techniques.

Conclusion

**Alphonsus Ekejiuba Oguzie, Ph.D, Eberechukwu Francisca Chigbu, Ph.D, Nwobi
Ngozika Lovina, Ph.D and Obianuju Blessing Mokwelu, Ph.D**

From the findings of this study, the researchers concluded that the causes of social media addiction among secondary school students in Oyi local government area are low self-esteem, fear of missing out, peer influence, poor parental supervision, loneliness, instant gratification from social media and impulsivity. However, the findings showed that gender is not the causes of social media addiction among secondary school students in the area. The study was also concluded that the consequences of social media addiction are poor academic achievement, social isolation, depression, drug abuse, health problems such as eye strain, headache and fatigue, Interpersonal relationship problems, cyber fraud and sleeping disturbance, while low self-esteem, suicidal ideation and expose to cyberbullying are not part of the consequences of social media addiction among students. Finally, it was concluded that assertiveness training technique, self-management technique, social skill training, use of stimulus satiation on addicted students, cognitive behaviour therapy, bibliotherapeutic materials, cognitive restructuring and modelling techniques are the counselling strategies for curbing social media addiction among secondary school students in Oyi local

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government area, while positive reinforcement and systematic desensitization techniques are not part of the techniques used for curbing social media addiction in the area.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Awareness and sensitization programmes, workshops and seminars should be organized by government and non-governmental organizations (NGOs), to enlighten parents, guardians and teachers on the causes and dangers associated with social media addiction and need to refer students with such problem for professional counselling.
2. School Counsellors should ensure kin and objective observation on students' behaviours and guard against such behaviours that could engender social media addiction among secondary school students.
3. Teachers should observe their students and refer those who are addicted to social media for professional counselling.
4. Significant others such as parents and care-givers should monitor and regulate the rate at which their children and wards use social media.

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